

THE ROLE OF HUMAN CAPITAL IN ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT

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ABSTRACT

The growing shortage of staff and the so-called "staff gap" in this article are among the key issues on the world labor market today. While university graduates and professionals who have become masters of their craft cannot find work in their specialties, employers lose years to find specialists for key positions. This situation did not happen yesterday. New technologies, artificial intelligence and robots - all of which are said to be radically changing the labor market, leaving millions of people unemployed and further complicating the problem of human resources. The current system of training does not have time to adapt to these changes and is not able to meet the growing needs of the business in new forms of personnel. As a result, it is highlighted that the staffing gap has a significant impact on all sectors of the economy, entire countries, and almost all forms of business..

Introduction

Almost 11 years ago, the international community first spoke about the qualification gap (depth), one of the main barriers to innovation and economic growth. The pace of technological development and economic change have prompted scientists, government leaders and the world's leading entrepreneurs to start a debate about what kind of human capital is needed for a modern economy.

This problem is directly related to the modern economy of Uzbekistan. According to a survey conducted by HRC and ERGO Research and Advisory in June 2019

involving more than 100 companies operating in the country, 67% of these firms reported certain difficulties in hiring staff. Most of them claimed that the main problems were the lack of professional and professional qualifications and work experience of the candidates.

Literature review

The principal component of an organization is its human resource or 'people at work'. According to Leon C. Megginson from the national point of view Human Resources as, "the knowledge, skills, creative abilities, talents and aptitudes obtained in the population;

whereas from the view point of the individual enterprise, they represent the total of inherent abilities, acquired knowledge and skills as exemplified in the talents and aptitudes of its employees" [6].

Human resource has a paramount importance in the success of any organization because most of the problems in organizational setting are human and social rather than physical, technical or economical failure. In the words of Oliver Sheldon, "No industry can be rendered efficient so long as the basic fact remains unrecognized that it is principally human" [7].

In the second half of last year, the Boston Consulting Group (BCG) released the results of a study entitled "Mass Identity: Global Challenges in the Struggle for Talent". The international study, which involved experts from 30 countries and more than 160 companies from 47 countries, looked at the causes of the growing problem of staffing gaps. BCG's report proposes solutions to this problem based on the concept of a "human-centered system" and mass identity. According to the authors of the study, taking the necessary measures in accordance with these solutions and proposals will not only harmonize the training systems and the labor market, but also provide an additional 0.5 to 2 percent growth in GDP.

In today's world, it is common for employers not to be able to find the specialists they need because there are no such specialists on the market. Companies are forced to hire people who don't have the necessary skills and experience and then invest in retraining them. Nevertheless, the state continues to fund funding for the education of professionals whose skills and competencies are not in

demand or who are redundant in the labor market. These requirements are changing even more before students graduate before educational institutions can train staff to meet the current needs of employers.

However, a person with sufficient work experience is at risk of losing the relevance of his skills and abilities and a sharp decline in demand for his skills and experience in the labor market. He is not able or willing to learn new, necessary skills. This problem, called the staff gap, exists in every country.

In the context of a vacancy, employers are often forced to hire employees whose qualifications roughly meet the required requirements. Most employees will agree to any job because they do not have jobs that match their qualifications. In this way, they replace the candidate with the appropriate qualifications and experience. This problem, called the qualification gap, is less noticeable than the problem of staffing gaps, because economic and social stability and the resulting superficial employment hide this problem to some extent. According to BCG Consulting, to date, the qualification gap problem is directly related to the world's nearly 1.3 billion people. This represents 6 percent of the hidden tax in the form of lost labor productivity in the global economy.

The technological changes of the early twentieth century and the industrial revolution, as well as the digital revolution of the late twentieth century, had a profound effect on the training system. First, the task of eradicating illiteracy was set, and then there was a need to improve the quality of education to meet the needs of key sectors of the economy. Secondary and higher education has become a universal currency that can be exchanged

for at least one profession. In those days, one profession lasted a lifetime. Gradually, the process of education lengthened, and quality education became increasingly expensive. Over the last half century, the average education duration has increased 2.5 times worldwide, while four-year budget education has tripled in the last 30 years.

With the advent of the 21st century, the world is changing faster. Emerging new technologies and new types of business are increasing the demand for new specialties and specialties. The old system of training does not meet the requirements of the labor market. If in the middle of the twentieth century the period of obsolescence of technical knowledge was ten years, now this period has been reduced to two to five years. The qualification gap (gap) arises as we continue to develop human capital, which took place in the middle of the twentieth century, in a completely different economic and social context.

Mass standardization is the same lifelong education and the same profession does not work in today's world. In the context of rapidly changing technologies and economic changes, human beings are required to think critically, to learn quickly and constantly, and to be agile.

In future numbers:

- ✚ By 2030, the world's population is expected to grow by 13 percent
- ✚ Due to automation and digitization, by 2035, 1/3 of employment will change
- ✚ 85% of the global workforce is low- and medium-skilled workers
- ✚ Today, 14% of all workload can be automated

We are accustomed to thinking about the future as a perfectly new stage of development that comes in the more distant future. Today, however, the pace and depth of change in all areas - economic, political, social, technological - has reached unprecedented speeds. These changes are not future trends. They are changing the labor market today at different speeds, at different scales and at different depths, everywhere, and all over the world. Changes in the labor market are taking place under the influence of megatrends. Such megatrends represent a wide range of structural changes that directly affect all aspects of human life. The authors of the report emphasize the following three groups of these megatrends: technological, socio-economic and cultural groups.

In the context of rapid technological development and constant market changes, it is necessary to ensure the appropriate dynamics and quality of human capital for economic growth. In countries with high GDP per capita and innovative economies, the share of highly qualified specialists is the highest in the world - from 22 to 45% (the average in the world - 15%). On the one hand, this legitimacy suggests that without the development of human capital, it is impossible to achieve further technical progress, solve socio-demographic problems and relevant cultural changes. On the other hand, it is well known that in the economy, highly qualified and suitable personnel do not emerge spontaneously. In the 21st century, the world economy is creating new demands for the quality and diversity of the workforce. But adapting to the new demands of the labor market in the education system takes some time.

There are some changes in the education system, but as before, the system

will have to answer a number of fundamental questions: How to approach education in a truly individual way, how to adapt it to the needs of each person? How can people be encouraged to pursue lifelong learning? How can students be guided to the necessary and desirable knowledge?

One of the main problems in the labor market during the transition to an innovative economy is the lack of qualified personnel. In the world, this problem is known as skills gap. One of the main reasons for the staffing problem is not the physical absence of specialist staff, but the mismatch of their knowledge and skills depending on the type of activity. According to the Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD), the qualifications of every third employee are either redundant or insufficient for the activities they perform. This so-called skills mismatch also applies to every second employer.

Qualifying numbers:

- ✚ 1.3 billion workers and employees face the problem of incompatibility with professional skills
- ✚ 45% of employers find it difficult to find workers and employees with the required qualifications
- ✚ 6% of labor productivity is lost due to incompatibility of skills in the member countries of the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD)
- ✚ 76% of workers and employees believe that they need to be prepared for the challenges of losing and finding a job in the future

- ✚ Global GDP is estimated at \$ 5 trillion due to relatively low labor productivity. is losing
- ✚ In the modern world, technical knowledge becomes obsolete in 2-5 years
- ✚ The cost of education has increased 2-3 times in the last 30 years

Over-qualified workers and employees for their positions could claim positions in most types of activities that require highly productive labor resources. For example, in the United States in 1970, the share of taxi drivers with a college degree did not exceed 1 percent of the total. In 2013, such highly qualified taxi drivers accounted for 15 percent. The skills and abilities of these people could be applied with greater benefit to the economy and society. At the same time, insufficiently qualified personnel are not able to thoroughly analyze their work. They need to be retrained, and in some cases there is no point in training such personnel. This has a direct impact on the efficiency of employers.

Qualification is a serious risk to the growth of the world economy. This will lead to a slowdown in growth on a global scale and an increase in unearned income. In 2016, the decline in labor productivity due to staff imbalances in OECD countries averaged 6 percent. The economic consequence of the qualification package is a hidden tax on labor productivity. When hiring an employee with insufficient qualifications, the employer either loses efficiency and does not receive the intended benefit, or is forced to train or retrain such an employee.

Qualification is not just an economic problem. It is an issue that threatens the stability and well-being of society, creating

a state of ambiguity and anxiety among employees about their future employment. Finally, the problem of inconsistency of the skills required and available in the employee poses a risk to the state as well. In the medium and long term, we can expect a further increase in the imbalance between countries in terms of economic growth and global division of labor. Only countries whose labor resources are ready for the maximum high-tech economy - the knowledge economy - can be competitive in the future.

Moving towards a knowledge economy requires employees to be able to work with a universal set of 21st century digital technologies and skills. The number of specialties in the world is growing, most of which have emerged in the last 10-15 years. Technical skills are becoming obsolete faster than the average duration of training a highly qualified specialist. However, the system of human capital formation still retains the old approach. This approach is to standardize education and centralize the education and labor market. The process of training personnel with standardized knowledge and skills is still ongoing. These unskilled workers continue to enter the labor market, which means that the qualification gap is widening. Attempts to adapt the education system to the new requirements of the market without changing its old approach lead to further complication of the existing problem. As a result, the duration of training is longer and more expensive.

A BCG survey of employees on job prospects showed the following:

- ✚ Every second employee believes that in the future his chances of finding a job will decrease

- ✚ 76% of employees are convinced that they should be prepared for future difficulties in finding a job
- ✚ 30% of ordinary employees and managers expect an increase in the level of skills required for successful operation in the next 3-5 years
- ✚ More than 30 percent of employees stated that they had no preparation for future changes.

The main mechanisms for the implementation of the social contract of the twentieth century are standardized professions, standardized education in these professions, the local labor market, a certain wage system, the employment of graduates of higher education institutions by distribution, and so on.

It is almost impossible to eliminate the qualification gap under such a social contract. Because the uneven distribution of human capital lies at the heart of the idea of standardization. This problem can be solved only in the case of a radical change in the social contract between the employee, the employer, the state and the education system.

The main task of the new social contract is to provide employees with a wide range of opportunities for training and employment. In turn, the employee assumes all responsibility for maximizing their potential. To do this, the education system must be a mediator between the needs of the employer, the state and the individual. Such a system should form a set of tools and methods necessary for a person's lifelong learning. The task of the employer is to select employees based on their real skills and abilities, not formal education, to create opportunities for them to express themselves in the workplace, taking into account their personal dignity.

The state, on the other hand, must create employment and development opportunities for everyone, taking into account their wishes.

Global issues in numbers:

- ✚ By 2022, the share of new activities will reach 27%
- ✚ 30% of workers and employees do not believe that they will be ready for the expected changes in the labor market in the future
- ✚ 49% of the world's population does not have access to the Internet

Changing the terms of the social contract - the transition from mass standardization to mass individuality - places new demands on a person's ability, motivation, and ability in the labor market.

In cases of high ambiguity, employees need to have all the necessary skills and knowledge to be able to adapt quickly to the changing demands of employers. This factor allows it to be always needed in the labor market. The state must ensure equal access to development and employment opportunities for all, and employers must create non-discriminatory conditions in the hiring of workers. The education system, in turn, is required to develop new approaches to training, taking into account the ever-changing requirements of employers.

Based on the principles of a person-centered system, the following seven conditions are envisaged: sustainable development, future skills, conscious independence, a barrier-free labor market, capacity mobilization, an inclusive labor market and respect for values.

These conditions are divided into three groups: "Abilities", "Motivation" and "Opportunities" and are described as follows:

- ✚ Ability: the formation of future skills and continuous human development
- ✚ Motivation: a person is the customer of his education and development
- ✚ Opportunities: employment based on the employee's qualifications, taking into account the values.

How far is the current labor market from the concept of a human-centered system?

Conclusion

The approach to a person-centered system is not an abstract humanistic concept, but rather to increase labor productivity, reduce the cost of searching and retraining specialists, improving the brand of the employer, and so on. Some components and aspects of this approach are used in business, as well as in the formulation of national strategies for the development of the labor market and education. However, building a completely new relationship system is a long and complicated process.

BCG research shows that the labor market in countries with large qualification gaps is characterized by a low level of human-centered system. In turn, the human-centered system is directly related to labor productivity: in countries with a high level of human-centered system, labor productivity is also much higher.

REFERENCES:

1. Abduraxmonov K., Zokirova H. Labour Economics and Sociology: Edited by Prof.Dr. E.S. Margianti, SE., MM. Tutorial. - Jakarta.: Gunadarma Publishet, 2013. –430 r.
2. Abdurahmonov Q.X., Shoyusupova N.T. Employment of the population. Study guide. - T.: 2011. - 291 p.
3. Kholmominov Sh.R., Kholmurodov S.E. Labor market economy. Study guide. - T.: 2013. - 228 p.
4. Kholmominov SH.R. Labor market economy. Study guide. - T.: Publishing House of the Literary Fund of the Writers' Union of Uzbekistan, 2004. - 144 p.
5. Video conference "On the effectiveness of reforms in higher education and the process of preparation for the new academic year" on June 16, 2021, chaired by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh. Mirziyoyev.
6. Leon C. Megginson, Personnel and Human resources Administration, Richard D. Irwin Inc. Homewood, Illinois 1977
7. Human Resource Management, Geet S.D., Deshpande A.D. & Mrs. Deshpande Asmita A., NIRALIPRAKASHAN, First Edition, Jan. 2009, P.24
8. A. Yulchiev, O. Axunova, O. Teshabaeva. ANALYSIS OF THE STATUS, MOVEMENT AND LEVEL OF FUNDING OF FUND FUNDS IN FOREIGN ENTERPRISES. ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal <https://saarj.com>
9. Sofiev R.A. Axunova O.E., Nematova Sh. E.. The current state of the cocktail market in Uzbekistan. NOVATEUR PUBLICATIONS JournalNX- A Multidisciplinary Peer Reviewed Journal. ISSN No: 2581 - 4230 VOLUME 7, ISSUE 3, Mar. -2021
10. O. Axunova, Z. Salimjonova. Modern marketing concepts to increase the competitiveness of national goods. Студенческий: научный журнал.Сибак. Новосибирск: Изд. ООО «СибАК», 2021. – 108 с. – Электрон. версия. печ. публ. – [https://sibac.info/archive/journal/student/3\(131_3\).pdf](https://sibac.info/archive/journal/student/3(131_3).pdf).
11. О.Э Ахунова. РОЛЬ ГОСУДАРСТВА В УПРАВЛЕНИИ ИННОВАЦИОННОЙ ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТЬЮ НА ПРЕДПРИЯТИЯХ РЕСПУБЛИКИ УЗБЕКИСТАН. Развитие территорий. Сибирский институт управления–филиал Федерального государственного бюджетного образовательного учреждения высшего профессионального образования «Российская академия народного хозяйства и государственной службы при Президенте Российской Федерации»
12. www.economist.com